

MERLIN SECTORAL DESKTOP REVIEW: INSERT SECTOR TYPE HERE

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A NOTE ON REFERENCING: we need to maintain a strong chain of evidence. This is a core part of research practice. It is particularly important as more than one person will be adding to and developing these reviews over the life of the project and they will be used to inform and develop other tasks. Being able to track back to original source materials is essential. Please make sure this is possible, either using referencing software (e.g. ENDNOTE). If not possible please include links and doc details, such as author, year, title, publisher (in case links change, which they do as website get updated!). Footnotes can be used if you find this easier. If you copying chunks of text please include page numbers too. If you able to download and save documents (e.g. reports or statement provided as pdfs or word files) in a specific folder for each sectoral desktop review that would help enormously.

1 Introduction

Section 1 text will be common text across all sector desktop reviews – text to be inserted at a later date.

1.1 Purpose and objectives of desktop review

The desktop review is being undertaken as part of the efforts to understand thoroughly each of the sectors in the WP4. The outcome of this review will influence subsequent tasks in WP4, including policy analysis and formation of roundtables. The main objectives of the review include:

- To identify the sectoral issues and how the sector depends on, or affects, freshwater restoration, and how restoration will impact their sector (double materiality issue)
- To identify the windows of influence in the sector and how they can be adopted to promote restoration
- To identify key sectoral themes, gaps, and opportunities for transformative restoration
- To gather data and information to inform the roundtables (and eventually later tasks in WP4).

To achieve the above objectives, the review will capture the following contents:

- Description of each sector and relationship with rivers/wetlands and with restoration
- Identification of environmental, social and economic challenges for the sectors
- Framing of transformation in the sector and how the known barriers/ gaps and opportunities for achieving restoration
- Main EU level sector policies, actors and decision-making processes
- EU Policy instruments and standards
- Key dimensions of sectoral value-chains

1.2 Methodology

Undertaking each review has involved the following steps;

- Agree aims, scope and develop team (who is doing what sector reviews)
- Develop template
- Regular review progress – careful and rigorous discussion to develop and maintain a common approach across the team. E.g. we discussed a lot the scope of the review, such as how to take a nested approach to set out vertical connections (e.g. peat/ peat extraction; energy/ renewable energy/ hydropower).
- Focus on grey literature with relevant literature added later
- Data collection

- First, a wide range of documents (e.g. reports, position papers and website content) produced by EU sector actors (private and public) were identified through search engines (e.g. Scopus) using diverse search terms (give an example?).
- Second, additional material was sourced, e.g. through tracing documents from the primary search through citations.
- Search terms were also widened as a better understanding of language used in each sector relevant to socio-environmental challenges and ecological restoration developed.
- Sections of text were then identified and extracted for analysis.
- Inductive analysis – identify and explain key ideas found across the documents and identify any potential implications for MERLIN for developing transformation strategies to mainstream NBS in the sector. NOTE: this will be an internal document used to inform future activities in WP4.

1.3 Definitions in MERLIN

Nature-based solutions (Nbs) are “actions to protect, sustainably manage, and restore natural or modified ecosystems, that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits.” (IUCN, 2016).

Restoration is defined as the process of assisting the recovery of an ecosystem that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed. Restoration involves active measures that seek to assist recovery of native ecosystems and ecosystem integrity. Restoration is therefore a deliberate process (that can involve a range of different activities), and recovery of ecosystem integrity (i.e. ecosystem functions) the desired outcome. Restoration is a means by which socio-ecological resilience can be strengthened (Gann et al., 2019).

Mainstreaming of Nbs means the routine informed inclusion of Nbs as an integral part of freshwater management practice into the decisions of institutions that drive the development policy, rules, plans, investment and action, enabling more widespread adoption (upscaling) of Nbs for restoring degraded freshwater ecosystems (Nunan, Campbell, & Foster, 2012).

Transformation is a meaningful (i.e. significant) systemic change (O'Brien, 2012). The focus and goal of transformation varies, e.g. it can and often is used with a focus on society as a whole (that includes policy, business and the public) and an example of a transformational process is achieving the goal net zero carbon emissions (Linnér & Wibeck, 2020). In MERLIN, our focus is to and upscale NbS across economic sectors at the EU level for freshwater ecosystem restoration. There are multiple approaches for shaping transformative change (Avelino et al., 2019; Scoones et al., 2020). In MERLIN the focus is on public and private sector policies and institutions to guide transformative future pathways.

2 Description of [insert sector name here] sector

2.1 Background of the sector, activities and sub-sectors

2.2 Challenges in the sector

2.2.1 Environmental challenges

2.2.2 Socio-economic challenges

2.3 Sector relationship with restoration

2.4 Past and current restoration measures

3 Framing the transformation in sectoral restoration

3.1 Meaning of transformation as discussed within the sector

3.2 Strategies for transformation in the sector

3.3 Barriers in mainstreaming restoration and Nbs

- i. **Policy and regulatory barriers**
- ii. **Administrative barriers**
- iii. **Objective barriers**
- iv. **Funding barriers**
- v. **Capacity barriers**
- vi. **Knowledge and information barriers**
- vii. **Accountability barriers**
- viii. **Other**

3.4 Opportunities that could promote or enhance restoration

- i. **Policy and regulatory opportunities**
- ii. **Administrative opportunities**
- iii. **Objective opportunities**
- iv. **Funding opportunities**
- v. **Capacity opportunities**
- vi. **Knowledge and information opportunities**
- vii. **Accountability opportunities**
- viii. **Others**

4 Policy instruments and standards in the sector (T4.3 and T4.5)

- 4.1 Existing global governance frameworks and standards considered relevant by the sector
- 4.2 Existing policy and standards at the EU level considered relevant by the sector

5 Value chains (T4.4)

- 5.1 Production (actors and processes involved)
- 5.2 Processing (Actors and processes involved)
- 5.3 Marketing (Actors and processes)
- 5.4 Usage/consumptions (who are the consumers?)
- 5.5 After use (what happens next?)
- 5.6 Value chain opportunities

6 Actors and decision-making processes

- 6.1 Main actors related to sectors and the role in decision making processes
 - 6.1.1 Public actors
 - 6.1.2 Private
 - 6.1.3 Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and/or networks
 - 6.1.4 Other relevant actors
- 6.2 Decision making timetable

7 Conclusions and recommendations for engaging the sector in transformation

8 References

- Avelino, F., Wittmayer, J. M., Pel, B., Weaver, P., Dumitru, A., Haxeltine, A., . . . O'Riordan, T. (2019). Transformative social innovation and (dis)empowerment. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 145, 195-206. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2017.05.002>
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